

NERSC Technical Report No. 181

**Providers of airborne pictures, digital elevation models
and bathymetry data**

Final Report

from the

CEO "Inventory of Non-Space Data" project

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the project has been to generate a comprehensive, non-exhaustive metadata inventory of airborne pictures, digital elevation models (DEMs) and bathymetric data sets for INFEO. The project has identified new data sources and validated the contents of 4 existing CEO inventories, in accordance with Version 2.0 of CEO's metadata standard [1].

Data for two new inventories have been compiled during the project:

1. Airborne pictures for South-western Europe and the Benelux countries, i.e. Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and Belgium.
2. Topographic data, i.e. Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) for each European country, and the most important European-wide and world wide DEMs, as well as world-wide and European bathymetric data sets.

In addition, 4 existing inventories were updated to version 2.0 of CEO's metadata standard:

- topographic maps,
- thematic maps,
- airborne pictures of Central and Eastern Europe, and
- airborne pictures of Northern Europe and the British Isles.

The new and updated inventories have been generated using the Metadata Authoring Tool Version 2.0, and integrated into one homogenous inventory. This inventory has been delivered to CEO for inclusion in their new online information system INFEO.

The main results from the project are:

- The survey of airborne pictures in SW-Europe and Benelux resulted in response from 33 organisations, having 35 data sets and 6 services. The organisations were national/county mapping agencies, commercial companies and non-profit organisations (Table 5, p.10).
- In the survey of DEM and bathymetric data sets, 42 questionnaires were returned or completed from web, with 61 data sets and 5 services. The organisations were national/county mapping agencies, commercial companies and non-profit organisations (Table 6, p. 13).
- The MAT tool, version 2.0, was used to generate two new inventories in accordance with version 2 of CEO's metadata standard. These data have been exported from MAT as XML files, and delivered to CEO for ingestion into INFEO.
- The update of the old inventories of airborne pictures resulted in 40 organisations (mainly in Central and Eastern Europe), with 27 data sets. The organisations were national/county mapping agencies, commercial companies and non-profit organisations (Table 7, p. 16).
- The update of the old inventory of thematic maps resulted in 32 organisations with 46 data sets. The organisations were mainly public institutions (Table 8, p. 17).
- The update of the old inventory of topographic maps resulted in 9 organisations with 10 data sets. Four organisations were public; the rest commercial (Table 9, p. 17).
- For each inventory, the URLs and postal addresses were checked, and new/modified URLs and addresses recorded. The results of this integrity check are found in Table 10 (on page 18) and Table 11 (p. 19).
- Finally, all MAT export files were integrated in a ZIP archive and delivered to CEO.

1. Introduction

Today many research and application projects using Earth Observation data have a trans-national character and require data from several countries and different sources. A large amount of spatial data are generated from several satellite programmes, which are applicable in many thematic fields. Non-satellite data, such as topographical data, are often needed to perform a more accurate analysis of the satellite data, but these data are typically provided by other companies making it difficult to find suitable pairs of satellite and non-satellite data sets. Thus, an online inventory with information about available non-space data will help users of Earth Observation data. Preparing information for such an inventory has been the purpose of this project.

To access inventories of inhomogeneous data sets via CEO's INFEO¹ (INFormation about Earth Observation) online information system, it is necessary to harmonise the description of data available from various providers. Development of a metadata standard is necessary because terminology and data description for satellite data as well as non-satellite data vary from one discipline to another. "Metadata attributes", for example, can have different meaning for different users of data. In order to access a wider range of data types via INFEO, it is essential to have a uniform way of specifying metadata.

CEO has identified several non-satellite data types that are of special importance for the development of Earth Observation applications. CEO has generated metadata inventories for these data types, which include airborne images, thematic maps and topographic maps, and also described associated services offered by the data providers. Each inventory adheres to the same specification, which is defined in the CEO metadata recommendations [1]. The information in these inventories is searchable in INFEO, and is freely available to all Internet users world-wide. This approach ensures that a wide range of data holdings and services as well as their dissemination policies are listed in one database.

INFEO is implemented by CEO as "a means of bringing together producers and users of earth observation products and services in order to encourage greater use". Besides data catalogues, it also provides a tutorial, answers to frequently asked questions (FAQs) about accessing the data catalogues and about what other information is found in the system, as well as access to software that can be downloaded. INFEO also provides a searchable interface to information about EO-related events, projects, organisations, persons and documentation. This provides a one-stop-shop for users that need to find different types of EO-related information quickly, to support their current or planned research or commercial work.

The project results are presented as follows. Section 2 is a description of the history of aerial photography with discussion of the problems of archiving these data. Results from the survey of airborne pictures in SW-Europe and Benelux countries are described in Section 3, and results from the survey of DEM and bathymetric data sets in Section 4. The experience of using the MAT-2 tool to generate the new inventories according to CEO's metadata standard version 2 is described in Section 5. The process of generating the new inventories, updating the 4 existing ones, performing integrity check of URLs and postal addresses, and integrating all 6 inventories in an archive, which has been delivered to CEO, is described in sections 6-9. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 10.

¹ <http://info.ceo.org/>

2. History of Aerial Photography

The history of aerial photography goes back to the early days of photography. The first permanent images made by the direct action of light were produced by the French amateur scientist Joseph Nicéphore Niepce, his first "heliographs" as he called them, were made in 1822 but proved to be impractical due to the extremely long exposures needed.

The first practical camera-imaging process was discovered by another Frenchman, Louis Jacques Mandé Daguerre, first published in 1839, called "daguerreotype", and although long exposures in direct sunlight was still needed, it was a success. Soon another invention appeared when an English scientist, John Goddard, discovered in 1840 that a silver-bromide/silver iodide coating gave much better sensitivity.

Although the daguerreotype was the first photographic process to be put to general use, the technique did not push the development of modern photography. A more successful technique was the calotype process invented by William Henry Fox Talbot in 1835, who discovered the principle that a negative-positive process with a fixing method was suitable and thus set the basis for modern photography.

Much history has since passed, such as colour photography, inventions in cameras and lenses, but will not be described in this report, but some historical facts in aerial photography from aerial platforms will be mentioned.

The first reference to photography from the air was made by the French physicist D.F. Arago in August 1839, shortly after the birth of the daguerreotype process. The first person to actually take an aerial photograph was another Frenchman, Gaspard Felix Tournachon ("Nadar"), who used a wet-collodion process successfully, from a captive balloon in 1858. This avid photographer and balloonist made this after many failures and attempts.

His first image was made at 80 meters over the village of Petit Bicêtre, near Paris but unfortunately, this image no longer exists. The earliest surviving aerial photograph is one taken in 1860 over the city of Boston, USA, by S.A. King and J.W. Black at a height of 630 meters using the wet-collodion process.

In 1858, the same year as Nadar captured his image, Colonel Aimé Laussedat of the French Corps of Engineers ascended in a balloon to make aerial images of Paris. That capture came after he had researched the possibility of using aerial images for preparing topographic maps since 1849 and in 1898 he presented a mathematical paper proving that it was possible to convert overlapping perspective photographs into orthographic projections on a plane.

As photography developed and the gelatine/silver bromide plates by Maddox in 1871 it became possible to delay the processing of photographic plates, and thus images could be processed at a later date. That set the standard for the modern photography from aerial platforms. It opened up the possibility of using other flying objects, such as kites. The first to take successful photographs from kites was the English meteorologist E.D. Archibald but using kites was then a standard method in gaining meteorological data.

Another use of kites was demonstrated by Batut of Paris, who in 1890 used a fused shutter release to trigger the exposure. By the year 1895 the American W.A. Eddy used a film camera to take photographs with a slow-match shutter–release mechanism.

The most famous kite aerial photography is one from American G.R. Lawrence who took pictures as large as 1350 x 240 mm with cameras weighing more than 400 kilos. He was able to send his camera system to an altitude of 1000 meters and one of his greatest achievements was to photograph the great fire of San Francisco on 18th April 1906.

The history of aerial photography before the invention of the first aeroplane includes trials with pigeons by Julius Neubronner of Germany, who invented a 70 gr tiny camera that took 38 mm square images and with the known flight line of the pigeon to its destination it was possible to gain useful pictures. The use of rockets for aerial photography was patented in 1891 but the first useful system was not made until 1912 by Alfred Maul. He employed a gyroscopically stabilised camera system weighing about 40 kilos and was able to lift the load by rocket to 800 meters. Once airborne to maximum altitude, the cone section was blown off and camera was released on a parachute. Exposures were then made with a special timing device.

All of these methods were impractical and the balloons, kites and pigeons had been thoroughly exploited. There was a great need for navigable aircraft. That was in theory ready in 1903 but surprisingly it was not until 1909 that the first aerial images from an aircraft heavier than air were taken. A passenger took them when he was flying with Wilbur Wright at an exhibition flight in Italy.

All further development of using aeroplane as an aerial camera platform was devoted to military purposes in the years prior to and during World War I. Even during that conflict some developments were made for more peaceful purposes. Much history transpired during early military applications and many of them closely connected to the inventions in aircraft building.

In the early 1920's, many commercial companies were starting up as aerial photography contractors. Amongst those who were formed was the British Air Survey Company, Abrahams Aerial Survey Corporation (USA), Hansa Luftbild in Germany and KLM Aerocarto in the Netherlands.

In the early 1930's, a large number of survey firms had been established some evolving from military operations in that field. The American Society of Photogrammetrists was founded in 1934 and thus placed aerial photography as a serious scientific application. Major advancements had been made in aerial photography by the late 1930's and the techniques became mature in the early 1950's. Apart from the technical advancements due to the previous wars there was also significant academic developments. In 1951 Dr. Schernerhorn, prime minister of the Netherlands, who was a well known photogrammetrist, formed the International Technical Centre for aerial photography, the ITC. Another milestone was in 1952 when the British Photogrammetric Society was founded.

Military use was more concerned with gathering intelligence data and later it developed into early mapping methods. Col. Aimé Laussedat takes the honour of using perspective photographs to make maps and has been called the father of photogrammetry. All these

historical developments made the aerial photography a viable and important aid in variety of applications. Camera systems were developed further, but a detailed description would be outside the scope of this report.

The transition of aerial photography from military operations into the commercial field has gradually evolved. State-owned companies, usually the mapping authorities, have been a large user and provider of aerial photography. The mapping authorities still have this role, but many of them have opted to buy the service from private companies specialising in aerial photography.

Future developments focus on digital image capturing to improve the geometric, radiometric and processing procedures. Important developments have been made in this area in the last few years. However, there seems to be a trend towards using hybrid systems since the digital capture has not yet challenged the film capture. Thus both current and new technologies are supporting each other to achieve the quality needed and at a cost acceptable for the customers. All the developments in the past have made aerial photography an important means of obtaining a large amount of earth data in an economical way for many applications.

Another important development is the very high resolution satellite systems like the recently launched IKONOS system. With a resolution of 1 meter and a visiting frequency of 3 days it forms the link between spaceborne and airborne remote sensing.

Data holders

In general the National Mapping Agencies (NMA's) are the most important holders of airborne pictures. In all countries, included in this survey, the NMA's have several data sets that cover the whole country. In most countries the oldest pictures in the archives of NMA's are made around 1930 and most of the NMA's were originally military organisations. The NMA's commercialize their products themselves or they've created special organisations for this purpose (especially the last 10 years), to be able to operate in a market-oriented way. All NMA's have an Internet-site where users can search for pictures and order products.

Also other national and regional institutions, like Ministries and regional public institutions, own data sets with airborne pictures. These data sets cover regions and not the whole country. Some of these institutions are included in this survey, but it is expected that more institutions are in the possession of airborne pictures. Because in general, these institutions do not commercialize their pictures, it is difficult to trace the data sets.

In all countries, included in this survey, private companies are active in the aerial photography business. Most of the companies are small scale but there are a few big companies as well. Some companies are dedicated to oblique and vertical aerial photography. All the companies have data sets with airborne pictures in their archives, dating many years back, and offer services like aerial flight services.

Archiving problems for aerial photography

Except from large organisations like KLM Aerocarto, Eurosense, Hansa Luftbild, etc., the European aerial service industry is characterized by numerous small-size organisations that perform aerial survey on request. Whereas the large companies cover large areas, most of the

surveys of the smaller organizations may vary from impressionistic photographs to dedicated research demands on small areas. Most of the cases are characterized by *ad hoc* aerial surveys that are not particularly characterized by a repetitive theme or topographic area. This makes the archiving of the huge amount of photographs about various topics time consuming and thus costly, particularly for these small-size organisations.

Through this inventory though we noticed that these organisations are orienting about the whereabouts of archiving their data sets in order to improve client services. This might make the INFEO instrument attractive to them within a few years from now. Currently though they consider the data inventory and the accompanied questionnaire to time-consuming or not (yet) to their interest. We recommend to contact the companies again within one or two years when INFEO is completely transparent and is no longer in its 'childhood'. When INFEO has shown its efficiency and benefits to this sector the organizations might be interested to join. We therefore also recommend to make a hit list of the relevant INFEO pages. It is our impression that particularly for the small-scale organizations INFEO is only valuable and worthwhile to spend a few hours on the inventory if their potential clients can find them as a service company; whether they have an archive or not.

3. Survey of airborne pictures of SW-Europe and Benelux

3.1 Inventory approach

The first step in this inventory was a literature and Internet research to identify data holders for the SW-Europe and Benelux countries. Then, the CEO metadata recommendations and earlier questionnaires were studied. All organisations, institutions and companies that are selling or processing airborne data were included in the list of potential participants who could provide information for the inventory.

Apart from Internet research the following resources were consulted: (1) monthly and yearly papers, magazines like BCRS (Beleidscommissie Remote Sensing), VI-matrix, GIS Europe and project reports, (2) direct telephone-communication with contact persons, and (3) library research.

3.2 Inventory results

As a result, an interim list was composed with all potential participants. Table 1 gives an overview of potential participants in each country.

Table 1: Overview of organisations/companies that received the invitation for participation

Type of Organisation	Belgium	France	Italy	Luxembourg	Netherlands	Portugal	Spain
Commercial	19	27	6	4	31	16	13
Government	7	13	5	1	6	6	6
Universities	1	2	5	1	2	0	5
Total per country	27	42	17	6	39	22	24

The list of potential participants that Synoptics made for airborne pictures was compared with the list that the NERSC prepared for the DEMs and bathymetric data. It was agreed that the NERSC would send the invitation to those organisations that appeared on both lists. The invitation was sent by e-mail, surface mail or fax. In total 177 organisations/companies were asked to participate in the inventory of airborne data. Of these, 164 (93%) indicated that they would like to participate. Figure 1 shows the distribution of these organisations.

Figure 1: Invitations sent in the airborne picture survey

The organisations/companies that were interested to provide information for the inventory, were asked to return a form with an expression of interest. Less than a fifth of the potential participants (18%) replied to the invitation spontaneously, and most of them had to be contacted by phone before they returned the form.

The results of the response are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of the response on the invitation (21 July 1999)

Total invitations	177
Number of responds	164
Interested in participating	45
Not interested in participating	119

It would have been more efficient to contact the potential participants by telephone first, instead of sending an e-mail or fax. It appeared that in many cases the invitation did not reach the right person the first time. About 50 times an extra e-mail or fax with the invitation had to be sent.

Table 3 gives an overview of the reasons why organisations were not interested in participating in the inventory. The most common reason is the fact that an organisation did not

work with airborne data or that the organisation did not have the license to sell airborne pictures. In 18 cases organisations were only dealing with satellite data; in 35 cases no reason was given. A big producer of airborne pictures, Eurosense, did not participate because it is against the policy of the company. Another company wanted to be paid for the information.

Table 3: Reasons for organisations not to join the questionnaire (21 July 1999)

Reason for not participating	Satellite data only	No licence	Other type of company, f.e. GIS-software	Services only	Other reason	No reason given
Number	18	13	22	27	4	35

After receiving a positive response by fax, e-mail or a positive answer by phone, the full questionnaire was sent. All interested organisations and companies were asked to fill in the questionnaire and to return it within a few weeks. Then again, a pro-active approach was required to ask for the filled-in questionnaires. This is a very time-consuming task. Often it is necessary to contact people more than one time before they really return the questionnaire. Apart from the phone-calls to the organisations that turned out not to be interested in participation, so far 164 phone-calls were made to achieve the return of 32 questionnaires (excl. phone-calls to organisations where the person to be contacted was not at that moment or organisations that do not want to participate). End of May 1999, 51 organisations and companies had confirmed their participation for the inventory of airborne pictures. After contacting the organisations again, to ask for the filled-in questionnaire, 6 companies decided not to participate in the inventory anymore, as they decided it to be too much work for them to fill in the questionnaire. Some judged that the inventory is not relevant for their company. At that time 45 organisations were participating, of which 38 returned the questionnaire. The number of participating organisations in each country is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Overview of organisations/companies that received the invitation and the questionnaire (27 October 1999)

Type of Organisation	Belgium		France		Italy		Luxembourg		Netherlands		Portugal		Spain	
	I	P	I	P	I	P	I	P	I	P	I	P	I	P
Commercial	19	4	27	3	6	1	4	0	31	14	16	4	13	1
Government	7	2	13	3	5	3	1	0	6	1	6	3	6	4
Universities	1	0	2	0	5	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	5	0
Sum	27	6	42	6	16	5	6	0	39	15	22	7	24	5
Ratio back	83%		83%		40%		0%		100%		86%		100%	

I = Received the invitation for participation.

P = Positive reaction on invitation; the questionnaire was sent after receipt of this reaction.

Ratio back = Percentage of returned questionnaires of interested organisations/companies (P).

At the end of the project, the final count of received questionnaires were 38, giving a response of 80% of the 44 organisations that had expressed interest in participating. Figure 2 shows the response on a country basis.

Figure 2: Response on completed questionnaires for airborne picture survey

Table 5 lists all the organisations for which the questionnaire is completed. Five of the organisations were done by NERSC, making the total of organisations completed by Synoptics 33. Together, the 33 organisations hold 35 data sets (relevant for this inventory) and 6 associated services.

Table 5: Organisations (Airborne pictures SW-Europe & Benelux) for which the questionnaire is completed

No.	Organisation/company, country	# data sets	# services	Type of data set
1	Airborne Platform for Earth Observation (APE-SAS), Italy	0	1	
2	CIMA, Italy	1	0	National DEM
3	IGN France International, France	1	0	Airborne pictures Luxembourg
4	GEOSYS S.A., France	3	1	Global DEM/ airborne pics
5	Inventaire Forestier National (IFN), France	1	0	Airborne pictures
6	INRA Bioclimatologie, France	1	0	Airborne pictures
7	EDIA, Portugal	3	1	Airborne, National DEM & bathymetry
8	ERFOTO LDA, Portugal	0	0	Only description of the organisation
9	Terracarta Consultoria Geomatica, Portugal	1	1	Airborne pictures, National DEM
10	Instituto Geografico do Exercicio (IGEOE), Portugal	1	0	Airborne pictures
11	Centro Nacional de Informacao Geografica (CNIG), Portugal	1	0	Airborne pictures
12	Consejeria de Medio Amb.- Junta Andalucia (CMA), Spain	1	0	National DEM & airborne pictures
13	Instituto de Cartografia de Andalucia (CICA), Spain	2	0	National DEM & airborne pictures
14	Ibersat S.A., Spain	1	0	Airborne pictures
15	National Institute for Aerospace Technology (INTA), Spain	0	0	Only description of the organisation
16	Meetkundige Dienst Rijkswaterstaat, the Netherlands	1	0	National DEM
17	Fleumer Aerophoto, the Netherlands	0	0	Only description of the organisation
18	De Jong Luchtfotografie, the Netherlands	0	0	Only description of the organisation
19	General Flight Services, the Netherlands	0	0	Only description of the organisation
20	Aerophoto-Schiphol BV, the Netherlands	1	0	Airborne pictures
21	Topografische Dienst Nederland, the Netherlands	3	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
22	Aluphoto, the Netherlands	0	0	Only description of the organisation
23	Air Photo Netten Corné, the Netherlands	0	0	Only description of the organisation
24	Slagboom en Peeters Luchtfotografie, the Netherlands	1	0	Airborne pictures
25	KLM Aerocarto BV, the Netherlands	0	0	Airborne pictures
26	Aero Lin Photo BV, the Netherlands	0	0	Airborne pictures
27	National Aerospace Laboratory (NLR), the Netherlands	0	1	Only description of the organisation
28	P. Geerders Consultancy, the Netherlands	3	0	Airborne pictures
29	TNO-Physics and Electronics Laboratory, the Netherlands	1	1	National SAR data
30	National Geographic Institute (NGI-IGN), Belgium	1	0	Airborne pictures
31	Aerodata Int. Surveys, Belgium	4	0	Global airborne pictures
32	N.A.D.A.R., Belgium	1	0	Global airborne pictures
33	Ministere wallon de l'Equipement & Transports (MET), Belgium	2	0	National airborne pictures
Total		35	6	

* topo - according to the old inventory of topographic maps these organisations also hold topographic data sets, but these were not inserted into the MAT-2 tool due to time constraints

4. Survey of DEM and bathymetry data

4.1 Compiling information about DEM and bathymetry data sets

Web and literature search was conducted in the beginning of the project to set up a list of potential data holders. This list was compared with that compiled by Synoptics, to ensure that we did not both contact the same organisation asking for the same information. For the survey of DEM and bathymetric data sets, 58 potential data holders were contacted.

All the organisations and companies on the initial list of data holders received a brief introduction letter, informing them about the project and what types of data we were looking for. This letter also included a short form, called the “Expression of Interest Form”, where they could give contact information and say which type of data they had that were relevant for the new inventory of non-space data. It was also possible to indicate other organisations or companies that may have suitable data, but we did not receive any suggestions from any of the replies to the invitation letter. About a dozen of the initial list replied positively to the invitation letter, and these got the questionnaire immediately afterwards. Only one of the organisations indicated that it had no relevant data for the inventory. The remaining organisations/companies on the initial list did not reply, and were contacted again.

A question sent to “Question & Answers” in the EWSE Forum resulted in 3 answers. First, one company (NPA Group, UK) wanted to participate in the inventory and asked for the questionnaire, which they also filled in and returned quickly. The two other answers were CEO personnel suggesting bathymetric data sets which may be included in the new inventory. For both of these data sets, GEBCO and bathymetry data for the Tasmanian region, we have contacted the respective data holder to obtain the required information, but neither of them replied before the deadline, and hence the information on their respective web sites were used as input for the new inventory.

Later in the project, as we found new potential data holders, we sent out a short description of the project along with the questionnaire. Thus, these did not get the invitation letter first, since they would then have to reply to invitation in order to get the questionnaire, and then use more time to fill in the full questionnaire afterwards.

The dissemination of invitation letters and questionnaires were made by e-mail and fax, because extensive use of telephone was found to be less cost-effective for this survey. When one dissemination method did not result in a reply, we tried the other method when reminding the data holders, or sent them a partially filled in questionnaire (based on information found on Internet) since several of the organisations we contacted “complained” about the information requested already being available on their organisation’s web site or from MEGRIN’s GDDD² inventory.

² MEGRIN (Multipurpose European Ground Related Information Network) is an organisation of National Mapping Agencies (NMAs) of Europe that was created in 1993 with the aim of helping the NMAs to meet the increasing demand for cross-border products and services. Among other activities, MEGRIN develops and maintains a metadata service freely accessible on the Internet, which provides standardised information on the main products available from the European NMAs. This service is called GDDD (Geographical Data Description Directory) and is available from <http://www.megrin.org/GDDD/Overview.html> MEGRIN's web site is at <http://www.megrin.org>.

4.2 Survey statistics

Invitations were sent to 58 organisations. Of these, 24 were National Mapping Agencies, 14 were in public sector in Europe, 12 were private companies (world-wide) and 7 organisations were located outside of Europe. Figure 3 shows the distribution of invitations on the different categories.

Of the contacted organisations, only 10 responded to the initial invitation, and 1 organisation stated that it had no data relevant for this inventory. The others had to be contacted again, and the questionnaire was sent to all organisations that did not reserve themselves. The results of the survey is shown in Figure 4, and can be summarised as follows:

- The questionnaire was completed for 18 of the National Mapping Agencies. One of these asked us to use information on their web pages to completed the form ourselves.
- The questionnaire was completed for 11 organisations in public sector in Europe. One of the replies was received via Synoptics.
- The questionnaire was completed for 7 private companies. Two of these replies were received via Synoptics.
- The questionnaire was completed for 6 non-European organisations.

Figure 3: Invitations sent in the DEM/bathymetry survey

Figure 4: Completed questionnaires for DEM/bathymetry survey

4.3 Inventory results

Table 6 lists the 42 organisations or companies for which the questionnaire is completed. Of these, 5 questionnaires were collected by SYNOPTICS, but inserted into MAT by NERSC because the organisation had DEM data or both DEM data and airborne pictures. Some questionnaires were filled in from web pages or other promotion material (marked with an * in Table 6). Two of the organisations specifically asked us to complete the questionnaire ourselves, using information found on their web pages (no. 28 and 29). For two organisations (no. 18 and 26) we only got a description of the organisation, and not of any of its data sets. Together, the 42 organisations hold 61 data sets (that are relevant for this inventory) and 5 associated services.

Table 6: Organisations holding DEM/bathy data for which the questionnaire is completed

No.	Organisation/company, country	# data sets	# services	Type of data set
1	NPA Group, UK	1	0	Global DEM
2	MEGRIN, France	1	0	Adm. Boundaries (topo)
3	Instituto Geografico Militare, Italy	4	0	National DEM (topo)
4	Administration du Cadastre et de la Topographie, Luxembourg	1	0	National DEM
5	National Geophysical Data Center, USA	3	0	Global DEM
6	Instituto Portugues de Cartografia e Cadastro, Portugal	2	2	National DEM (topo)
7	GETECH division of ULIS Ltd, UK	1	1	Global DEM
8	Institut Geographique National, France	4	0	National DEM (topo)
9	Geodetska Uprava Republike Slovenije	1	0	National DEM (topo)
10	Drzavna Geodetska Uprava, Croatia	2	0	National DEM (topo)
11	National Land Survey of Finland	1	0	National DEM (topo)
12	DaimlerChrysler Aerospace, Dornier Satellitensysteme GmbH, Germany	1	0	Local high res. DEM
13	National Mapping Agency of Austria	1	0	National DEM (topo)
14	NOAA National Geophysical Data Center, Marine Geology & Geophysics Division	1	0	Global bathymetry
15	Hellenic Military Geographical Service, Greece	3	0	National DEM (topo)
16	Ordnance Survey of Northern Ireland	1	0	National DEM (topo)
17	Kort & Matrikelstyrelsen (Nat.Mapping Agency), Denmark	1	0	National DEM (topo)
18	Landmælinger Íslands (Nat.Mapping Agency), Iceland	0	0	
19	Statens Kartverk (Nat.Mapping Agency), Norway	1	0	National DEM (topo)
20	Gesellschaft für Angewandte Fernerkundung mbH, Germany	1	0	DEM Europe
*21	Centro Nacional de Información Geografica (CNIG), Spain	1	0	National DEM
22	ARGOSS, the Netherlands	1	1	Global coastal bathymetry
23	Aquaterra N.V., Belgium	3	1	National DEM
24	Consejería de Medio Ambiente-Junta de Andalucía, Spain	2	0	National/Local DEM
25	Bundesamt fuer Kartographie und Geodaesie, Germany	3	0	National DEM
*26	Datorkarte Ltd., Latvia	0	0	
27	University of Liege, Belgium	1	0	Regional bathymetry
*28	Bundesamt für Landestopographie, Switzerland	2	0	National DEM (topo)
*29	EROS Data Center, Sioux Falls, SD, (USGS), USA	1	0	Global DEM
*30	Lantmäteriverket (Nat.Mapping Agency), Sweden	1	0	National DEM (topo)
*31	BODC, British Oce. Data Centre, UK	1	0	Global bathymetry
*32	National Snow and Ice Data Center, USA	1	0	Regional bathymetry
*33	Ordnance Survey, UK	2	0	National DEM (topo)
*34	Australian Geological Survey Organisation, Australia	1	0	Regional bathymetry
*35	Naval Ocean. Office Dept. of Defence, USA	1	0	Global bathymetry
*36	Bureau de recherches géologiques et minières (BRGM), France	1	0	Global DEM
*37	Bayerisches Landesvermessungsamt, Germany	1	0	County DEM (topo)
*38	Landesvermessungsamt Brandenburg, Germany	1	0	County DEM (topo)
*39	Hessisches Landesvermessungsamt, Germany	1	0	County DEM (topo)
*40	Landesvermessung+Geobasisinformation Niedersachsen, Germany	2	0	County DEM (topo)
*41	Landesvermessungsamt Rheinland-Pfalz., Germany	2	0	County DEM (topo)
*42	Landesvermessungsamt Schleswig-Holstein, Germany	1	0	County DEM (topo)
Total		61	5	

* topo - according to the old inventory of topographic maps these organisations also hold topographic data sets, but these were not inserted into the MAT-2 tool due to time constraints

5. The CEO version 2 metadata standard and the MAT-2 tool

A beta release of the Metadata Authoring Tool (MAT) tool was made available by CEO in August 1999, and installed at each partner's site and used to insert data into inventories according to CEO's metadata standard version 2.0 [1]. This tool is written in Java and can be used on PC and Solaris platforms, but in this project the partners only used the PC version.

Using MAT, the returned questionnaires for airborne pictures of Benelux and SW-Europe were inserted into the new metadata standard, and MAT2 export-files generated for ingestion in INFEO. Of the 38 questionnaires received by Synoptics, 5 were completed by NERSC because they also contained DEM data sets. The completed questionnaires for DEM and bathymetric data sets were also inserted into MAT, and exported as XML files for later inclusion in INFEO. Tabs 5 and 6 list the organisations for which data were compiled.

Most questionnaires were returned by email enabling copy and paste of the data into MAT, thus limiting typing errors. Those questionnaires returned by fax were typed into a text file before inserting data into MAT.

The questionnaires used in this project was based on CEO's metadata standard version 2.0, and the information returned was for a large part compatible with the MAT tool. However, some information could not be inserted due to limited choice possibilities. For instance, if an organisation operates on an international area (countries not specified), this could not be inserted into the field "spatial coverage" of the MAT tool. Information in questionnaires that could not be inserted into the MAT tool, was placed in the abstract of the organisation or data set. Missing e-mail addresses were retrieved by visiting the web site of the organisation.

The processing of the item "Additional services" into MAT was very time-consuming; for mentioning a service a lot of fields have to be completed, which are already done in the data set or organisation. It would be better to include this item of "Additional Services" into the data set or organisation itself. Another disadvantage of the MAT software is the difficulty to import exported files for updates or correction purposes (this accounts only for the files that are removed from the MAT-program); where necessary corrections were made in the ASCII-file using NoteTab.

The overall impression of the MAT tool (beta version) was that although it was easy to use, it was time consuming to input data, as the tool required a lot of pointing and clicking to open up input windows. Each of these windows contained just a few input fields, so a large number of windows had to be opened and closed for each of the resources (organisation, data set and service) that were inserted.

If feasible, the following improvements should be incorporated before the tool is made publically available:

- A more extensive user guide/tutorial should be made. There was a brief online (HTML) tutorial packaged with the beta version. This tutorial provided a basic description of terms used and functionality of the tool, but a more comprehensive manual is needed, to guide new users through the insertion process. A step by step guide for input of information about organisations, data sets, services, and the other resources that can be specified in the tool, should be prepared, including screen shots so that the user can relate the information his organisation is holding to the different parts (windows) of the MAT tool.

- The enhanced guide/tutorial should be available in both online and hardcopy format. An online version enabling the user quickly to locate information during insertion, and a paper version for users who prefer to read through the description of the tool's capabilities prior to starting the insertion process on their terminal.
- The tool has limited choice possibilities on some parameters, e.g. on the area where an organisation operates. For instance, if the organisation operates internationally (countries not specified), this could not be inserted into the field "spatial coverage" of the MAT tool.
- For organisations who will input a number of data sets, services, etc. the current layout of the user interface with lots of small windows with few input fields in each, will make the insertion process time consuming. Re-organising the user interface so that more information can be inserted into each window, will reduce the time needed to complete the insertion process.
- When exporting data from MAT, the tool verifies that all the mandatory fields in each resource is filled in. If not, a general error message stating that "The following resource has mandatory field(s) empty: Data set" is displayed on the screen. The user would save a lot of time if the tool reported *which field* was empty. Then, he/she could go straight to this field and input the missing data, instead of having to look through all fields, which requires opening and closing a lot of windows.

6. Generation of new inventories based on the two surveys

Using the MAT tool, the results from the two surveys for airborne pictures and DEM/bathymetry data were inserted into two inventories following the new metadata standard, and XML files exported for later ingestion in INFEO. Each organisation was exported as a separate XML file by the MAT tool, and these files can be read by INFEO.

The number of organisations and data sets in the new inventories are listed in Table 5 and 6.

7. Update of 4 existing inventories

The 4 old inventories contained a total of 127 organisations. Due to time constraints, only 81 of these were inserted into the MAT-2 tool.

The update of existing inventories holding airborne pictures from previous surveys resulted in 40 organisations (mainly Central and East European Countries), with 27 data sets (Table 7). The organisations were national/county mapping agencies, commercial companies and non-profit organisations. The setup of the survey of the existing questionnaires for airborne pictures was quite similar as the new inventories, thus suitable for inserting into the MAT tool, but unfortunately a large percentage of organisations (30%) had not filled in the data set description. All organisations from this inventory were entered into the MAT-2 tool.

The update of the old inventory of thematic maps resulted in 32 organisations (from Western Europe and Scandinavia) holding 46 data sets (Table 8). The organisations were mainly public institutions. All organisations from this inventory were entered into the MAT-2 tool.

The update of the old inventory of topographic maps resulted in 9 organisations having 10 data sets (Table 9). The organisations were evenly distributed between public institutions and commercial firms. Not all organisations from this inventory were entered into MAT-2.

The old inventories of thematic and topographic maps were organised in MAT-1 export files. These files were in ASCII format, with a similar structure as the XML files exported from the MAT-2 tool. However, each resource had been put in a separate file, and there was no linkage information available. Thus, the descriptions of organisations, data sets and persons, which belonged to the same organisation had to be matched manually before insertion into MAT-2 could begin. This made the preparation of these inventories in the new metadata standard a time consuming process. For this reason, only 9 of the 55 organisations in the old inventory of topographic maps were included. These 9 organisations were selected to complement those found in the other inventories, with focus on selecting national mapping agencies which did not respond to the DEM/bathymetry survey in this project (Slovakia, Hungary and Cyprus), and commercial companies that were not covered in the new survey. The organisations that overlapped with those in other inventories are marked with "topo" in Table 5-8.

Table 7: Organisations from the 2 old inventories of airborne pictures

No.	Organisation/company	Country	# data sets	# services	Type of data set
1	BEV Austria	Austria	1	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
2	Swisstopo	Switzerland	1	0	Airborne pictures
3	Eidgenoss. Vermessungs	Switzerland	1	0	Airborne pictures
4	LH Systems GmbH	Switzerland	0	0	Only description of the organisation
5	Swissphoto Vermes. AG	Switzerland	1	0	Airborne pictures
6	Argus Geo System s.r.o	Czech Rep.	1	0	Airborne pictures
7	Geodis BRNO, s.r.o.	Czech Rep.	1	0	Airborne pictures
8	AerowestPhoto.H.Benfer	Germany	0	0	Only description of the organisation
9	Badische Luftbildmes.	Germany	0	0	Only description of the organisation
10	Geoplana Ing. mbH	Germany	1	0	Airborne pictures
11	Hansa Luftbild GmbH	Germany	1	0	Airborne pictures
12	MAPS Geosystems	Germany	1	0	Airborne pictures
13	Photogrammetrie GmbH	Germany	1	0	Airborne pictures
14	Rall Air Luftbild GmbH	Germany	1	0	Airborne pictures
15	Terra-Bildmessflug	Germany	1	0	Airborne pictures
16	Aerophoto/photographic	Greece	1	0	Airborne pictures
17	Geomatics Ltd.	Greece	1	0	Airborne pictures
18	Carto Hansa KFT	Hungary	0	0	Only description of the organisation
19	Telecopter KFT	Hungary	0	0	Only description of the organisation
20	Inst. Geod., Carto, Rem.	Hungary	0	0	Only description of the organisation
21	Kort&Matrikelstryrelsen	Denmark	1	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
22	Scankort LLO Group	Denmark	0	0	Only description of the organisation
23	Kampsax Geoplan	Denmark	1	0	Airborne pictures
24	Matrikulstovan	Faroe Islands	1	0	Airborne pictures
25	Konekorhonen OY	Finland	0	0	Only description of the organisation
26	FM – Kartta OY	Finland	1	0	Airborne pictures
27	Maanmittauslaitos	Finland	1	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
28	Ordnance Survey	Great Britain	1	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
29	NERC	Great Britain	1	0	Airborne pictures
30	Hunting Aerofilms ltd.	Great Britain	0	0	Only description of the organisation
31	Landm. Islands	Iceland	1	0	Airborne pictures
32	Loftmyndir ehf	Iceland	1	0	Airborne pictures
33	Ordnance Survey of Ireland	Ireland	1	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
34	Ord. Survey Northern Ireland	N.Ireland	1	0	Airborne pictures
35	B.K.S. Surveys's	N. Ireland	0	0	Only description of the organisation
36	Fotonor AS	Norway	0	0	Airborne pictures
37	NLF	Norway	0	0	Only description of the organisation
38	Statens Kartverk	Norway	1	0	Airborne pictures (topo)
39	Bildmesstechnik Schwaben	Germany	0	0	Only description of the organisation
40	METRIA	Sweden	1	0	Airborne pictures
Total			27	0	

- Questionnaires returned to Synoptics without data sets are marked 0 in the number of data sets/services column above. This also applies for very incomplete returned data sets.

* topo - according to the old inventory of topographic maps these organisations also hold topographic data sets, but these were not inserted into the MAT-2 tool due to time constraints

Table 8: Organisations from the old inventory of thematic maps

No.	Organisation/company, country	# data sets	# services	Type of data set
1	BGR, Geological Survey of Germany	3	0	Geological maps of Europe and Germany
2	British Geological Survey, UK	1	0	Geological map of UK
3	Centro Interregionale, Italy	0	0	
4	Centro Nacional de Información Geográfica (C.N.I.G), Spain	1	0	CORINE land cover Spain (topo)
5	Centro Nacional de Informação Geográfica, Portugal	2	0	CORINE land cover and land cover cartography Portugal
6	Danish Institute of Plant and Soil Science (DIPS), Denmark	1	0	CORINE land cover Denmark
7	EEA, European Environmental Agency, Denmark	2	0	European Lakes Dams and Reservoir database CORINE biotopes sites db.
8	Winand Staring Centre SC-DLO	2	0	CORINE Neth., land cover
9	Federal Environment Agency Vienna, Austria	1	0	CORINE land cover Austria
10	G2ERE, Luxembourg	1	0	CORINE Luxembourg
11	GEUS, the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	2	0	GEUS soil type map Denm., top pre-Zech. S. Scandinavia
12	Geological Survey of Austria	1	0	Geological map Austria
13	Geological Survey of Norway	2	0	Geological maps Norway
14	Geological survey of Finland	4	0	Geological maps Finland
15	Geological survey of Ireland	1	0	Geological map Ireland
16	Geological survey of The Netherlands	1	0	Geological map the Nether.
17	HEMCO, Hellenic Mapping & Cadastral Organisation, Greece	1	0	CORINE land cover Greece
18	Institut Géographique National de Belgique / Nationaal. Geografisch Instituut van België, Belgium	1	0	Land use/cover Belgium
19	ITGE Geological Survey of Spain	1	0	Geological map Spain
20	Institut Français de l'Environnement (IFEN), France	1	0	CORINE land cover France
21	Institute of Hydrology, UK	2	0	Catchment boundaries, European Water Archive
22	Institute of Terrestrial Ecology - ITE, UK	3	0	Land Classification Great Br. Countryside Info.System UK Land cover map Great Br.
23	National Environmental Research Institute, Denmark (NERI)	1	0	Large river database
24	National Land Survey Finland	1	0	Land cover & forest class. Finland (topo)
25	National Land Survey of Iceland	1	0	Vegetation map Iceland
26	Norwegian Institute of Land Inventory, Norway	2	0	Landscape map/land use map
27	Ordnance Survey of Ireland (OSI)	1	0	CORINE land cover Ireland (topo)
28	SSC Satellitbild Aktiebolag, Sweden	1	0	Land cover types Sweden
29	State Geological Survey, Luxembourg	1	0	Geomorph.map Luxembourg
30	Statistisches Bundesamt Umweltökonomische Gesamtrechnungen, Germany	1	0	CORINE land cover Germany
31	The BRGM Group Geol. Survey of France	1	0	Geological map France
32	The Icelandic Institute of Natural History, Iceland	2	0	Geological maps Iceland
Tot:		46	0	

* topo - according to the old inventory of topographic maps these organisations also hold topographic data sets, but these were not inserted into the MAT-2 tool due to time constraints

Table 9: Organisations from the old inventory of topographic maps (*)

No.	Organisation/company, country	# data sets	# services	Type of data set
1	Geodetický a Kartografický Ústav, Slovakia (The National Mapping Agency of Slovakia)	1	0	Basic Territory Identification Register
2	Cyprus Department of Lands and Surveys	1	0	Cyprus Administrative Boundaries
3	Földmérési és Távérzékelési Intézet, Hungary (The National Mapping Agency of Hungary)	4	0	Various databases of Hungarian topography and boundaries
4	Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg, Baubehörde - Amt f. Geoinformation und Vermessung, Germany	4	0	digital city map, digital base map, Digital Regional Map, Aerial photographic map of Hamburg 1:5.000
5	GeoCenter International Landkartenhaus, Germany	0	0	
6	Eurosense Belfotop, Belgium	0	0	
7	TELE ATLAS, Belgium	0	0	
8	Blay Foldex, France	0	0	
9	Navigation Technologies	0	0	
Total		10	0	

(*) This inventory originally contained 55 organisations. Time constraints prohibited insertion of all organisations and data sets.

8. Integrity check of URLs and postal addresses

The URLs registered in the old inventories were checked, and corrected if the organisation had moved its web site. If the organisation did not have a web site at the time of the previous survey, it was checked if it had established a site now, by searching for the organisation name using an Internet search engine (such as Altavista). If a valid web site was not found, the associated input field in the MAT tool had to be left empty. Postal addresses for each of the organisations in the old inventories were also checked, and an address had changed, the new one was inserted into the MAT tool.

Table 10 shows the results of the URL integrity check for both the old and new inventories of airborne pictures. For these inventories, 4 web sites had changed their URLs, 6 new sites were found, and 19 organisations were still without their own web site. None of these organisations had changed their postal address.

Table 10: Results after URL integrity-check for inventories of airborne pictures.

	Number of URLs				
	total (a)	correct (b)	changed (c)	new (d)	without (e)
Airborne pictures SW-Europe & Benelux	28	26	2	0	5
Airborne pictures Central & Eastern Europe and the Northern Europe and the British Isles	26	18	2	6	14
Total	54	44	4	6	19

(a) = total number of web pages listed in the old inventory for either the organisation or its data sets

(b) = number of web pages that were still valid

(c) = number of web pages that had changed their URL

(d) = number of new URLs that were found for organisations/data sets not previously having one

(e) = no website

Concerning the new inventory of airborne pictures of Benelux and SW-Europe: 28 of the 33 organisations filled in their URL. After completing an integrity check 26 were correct and valid. By searching the Internet we were able to find the remaining 2 URLs making a total amount of 28 correct URLs. The web sites of the remaining 5 organisations could not be found after extensive searching on the Internet (see Table 7).

Of the 40 organisations in the existing inventories or airborne pictures of Central/Eastern Europe and of the British Isles/Northern Europe, 20 organisations had filled in their URL. After an integrity check 18 were correct and valid. By searching the Internet we were able to find the remaining 2 URLs and found 6 new URLs, making the total of 26 correct URLs. Web sites for the remaining 14 organisations could not be found. The inventories were updated with new or changed URLs. In total, 74 % of the participating organisations maintain a web site.

Table 11 shows the results of the URL integrity check for the new inventory of DEM/bathy data and of the old inventories of thematic and topographic maps. For these inventories 94 % of the web pages were still valid, while 6 % had changed its URL. In addition, 12 new web pages were found, and inserted into MAT. The search for new web pages provided no results for 13 of the organisations (of a total of 83 in all three inventories).

Many of the organisations in the old inventory of topographic maps overlapped with those in the newly compiled inventory on DEM and bathymetry data, and to a smaller degree with the old inventory of thematic maps and the new inventory of airborne pictures. Thus, we focused on entering organisations which were not already in the previously made inventories.

Table 11: Results after URL integrity-check for old inventories of thematic and topographic maps.

	Number of URLs				
	total (a)	correct (b)	changed (c)	new (d)	without (e)
DEM/Bathymetry data	40	40	0	0	7
Thematic maps	20	16	4	10	3
Topographic maps	4	4	0	2	3
Total	64	60	4	12	13

(a) = total number of web pages listed in the old inventory for either the organisation or its data sets

(b) = number of web pages that were still valid

(c) = number of web pages that had changed their URL

(d) = number of new URLs that were found for organisations/data sets not previously having one

(e) = no website

The postal address integrity check for the old inventories of thematic maps showed that 6 of the organisations had changed their address. For the old inventory of topography maps, 2 organisations had changed their postal address since the inventory was initially compiled.

Postal addresses for organisations in the DEM/Bathy inventory did not change during the data compilation phase.

9. Integration of all 6 inventories

Export files from MAT are on an organisation basis, i.e. each XML file contains data for one organisation. Thus, the grouping of related organisation was done on a file system basis, i.e. by making a directory for each inventory and putting the respective files in the corresponding directory. Table 12 shows the contents of the ZIP archive was delivered to CEO as the final result of the project. This file contained 5 ZIP archives, of which one contain two inventories.

Table 12: Structure of ZIP archive holding the integration of all 6 inventories

CEO-Inventory-of-Non-Space-Data.zip			
+----->	wp4000.zip	Contains the new inventory of airborne pictures collected in this project (See Table 5)	
+----->	DEM-Bathy.zip	Contains the new inventory of DEM data and bathymetries collected in this project (See Table 6)	
+----->	wp5000.zip	Contains the 2 old inventories of airborne pictures from Eastern & Central Europe, and from the Northern Europe and the British Isles (See Table 7)	
+----->	Thematic.zip	Contains the old inventory of thematic maps (See Table 8)	
+----->	Topographic.zip	Contains the old inventory of topographic maps (See Table 9)	

10. Conclusion

Aircraft observations used to be the most important remote sensing method before satellite earth observation became available. When high-resolution satellite images started to develop seriously in the 1970's with the Landsat programme, satellite images could be used in stead of aircraft photography in some applications which required large scale surveys. Aircraft remote sensing has many advantages compared to satellites such as very high resolution, flexible temporal and spatial coverage, observation from the below cloud cover, and the possibilities to have more advanced instrumentation onboard. Therefore, aircraft remote sensing can be used in many applications in spite of the fact that there is a wide range of satellite data available. Aircraft observations are particular important in cartographic mapping and have not yet been replaced by satellite data. Digital elevation models are mainly derived from aircraft stereophotography. However, with very high resolution satellite images (1 m pixels) and SAR interferometry it is expected that satellites will take over some of the market for aircraft remote sensing, especially in remote areas where use of aircraft is unpractical. In some applications, such as sea ice monitoring, forest fire monitoring, coastal pollution monitoring, satellite SAR data have to some extent replaced aircraft monitoring. But in most applications that need very high-resolution imaging, aircraft observations will still be the main data source. It is clear that satellites and aircraft have different, but often complementary roles in remote sensing, the former being most important in large scale regular surveying, while the latter is preferable for all local and small scale observations which only need to be repeated once in a while. Aircraft data can be very useful for development and validation of products from satellite data. Aircraft remote sensing is also a testbed for instruments which later will be flown in satellites.

The project has collected information on data and service providers for airborne pictures, digital elevation models and bathymetry data, which have been compiled in inventories available through the INFEO service. All inventories are prepared using CEO's metadata standard Version 2.0.

The survey of airborne picture providers was limited to ten countries in western and south-western Europe. Previous inventories of topographic maps, thematic maps and airborne pictures for other parts of Europe were updated and made accessible through INFEO. The survey of digital elevation models and bathymetry data included most of Europe.

The new inventories contain 33 organisations providing airborne pictures and 42 organisations providing digital elevation models and bathymetry data. The previous inventories contain 40 organisations for airborne pictures, 32 organisations for thematic maps and 9 organisations for topographic maps. The postal and URL addresses are checked and updated for all the organisations.

The inventories will facilitate access to information about airborne pictures, topographic data and related products, which are key data sets for development and validation of a wide range of satellite data products.

References

- [1] Recommendations on Metadata. Describing the data, services and information you have available! A User Guide provided by the Center for Earth Observation Programme (CEO programme) Of the European Commission Version 2.0, February 1999.